

Enterprise-wide Risk Management Drivers in the Mining Industry: Evidence from a Developing Economy

Luke Charles Chikosi and Ashley Teedzwi Mutezo

*Department of Finance, Risk Management and Banking, College of Economic Management Sciences (CEMS)
University of South Africa, Pretoria, South Africa*

On a global scale, there has been a significant paradigm shift in corporate risk management practices. Large amounts of evidence from the risk management literature show that firms are transitioning from silo-based to enterprise-wide risk management (EWRM) approaches to improve sustainability and shareholder value. However, as the business environment has become more complex and diverse, the drivers for EWRM adoption have shifted. The purpose of this paper is to investigate the relationship between EWRM drivers and EWRM implementation in the South African mining industry. A questionnaire survey using a five-point Likert scale was employed to collect quantitative primary data from 136 purposively sampled risk practitioners, representing 67 members of the Minerals Council South Africa (MICSA), for the financial year ended 31 March 2024. Using analysis of variance (ANOVA) and correlation analysis, the study found a positive and significant relationship between EWRM drivers and EWRM implementation. Furthermore, using normalised values, the study found 32 out of 34 drivers for EWRM to be critical in the South African mining sector. The findings of the study may contribute to the existing body of knowledge, mining entities' management, and regulators.

Keywords: Enterprise-wide risk management, critical drivers, mining sector, mineral council South Africa

Enterprises in various sectors of the global economy confront a wide range of risks that threaten their smooth operation, and mining firms are no exception (Lee et al., 2020). Global rivalry, pandemics, deregulation, downsizing, and technical advancements have made the corporate environment more complicated and dynamic (Božič & Dimovski, 2019; Tiberius et al., 2021). Risk management has become a key responsibility of mining enterprises' corporate governance bodies in this multifarious and dynamic environment, as firms face a greater range of complex hazards (Daniels et al., 2019; Tiberius et al., 2021). South African mining companies face a number of concerns, including energy shortages, corruption, regulatory changes, digital innovation, environmental and social challenges, skills shortages, decarbonisation, uncertain demand, and geopolitics (Spitz & Trudinger, 2019).

According to the Institute of Risk Management South Africa [IRMSA] (2021), the most crucial risks are governance failure,

economic slowdown, and a skills deficit. On the one hand, negative mining sector events such as the Marikana massacre in 2012, the Harmony Gold six-month strike in 2014, and a general drop in production of several main minerals raised mining companies' risk exposure. Nonetheless, the COVID-19 pandemic created occupational health and safety hazards for mining firms, reducing mine workers' productivity (Daniels et al., 2019; Magnusson et al., 2020; Stephany et al., 2020; Tiberius et al., 2021). When an economic sector encounters issues with the size of South Africa's mining sector, the need to handle risks holistically becomes imperative (Daniels et al., 2019). Mining businesses, on the other hand, have done an excellent job of revealing the important hazards they confront daily (Pekol, 2019).

However, the mining industry is facing challenges in adopting EWRM. Primarily, the mining industry is hazardous, making it challenging to adopt effective EWRM practices. The adoption of EWRM in the mining sector implies that every employee should be involved in managing risks faced by mining firms. Thus, the board of directors is compelled to ensure that every employee is trained to implement the risk management processes. Training employees requires funding, and some may resist the process of acquiring risk management skills, creating resentment and tension among personnel. Therefore, a specialised committee must be formed to handle holistic risk management and employee training. Moreover, the emergence of digitalisation, globalisation, and geopolitical dynamics has brought about new and complex risks that require constant modification of the EWRM frameworks and the acquisition of systems and tools to reduce risk exposure. Failure to review and update EWRM practices may lead to severe financial losses and reputational damage.

Thus, it is crucial to explore the critical drivers of EWRM implementation to reduce associated losses. This paper aims to explore the critical drivers for EWRM implementation in the South African mining sector. The following section discusses the relevant

Author Note

Luke Charles Chikosi, Department of Finance, Risk Management and Banking, College of Economic Management Sciences (CEMS) University of South Africa, Pretoria, South Africa

Luke Charles Chikosi: ORCID: 000-0001-9549-6878

Ashley Teedzwi Mutezo, Department of Finance, Risk Management and Banking, College of Economic Management Sciences (CEMS) University of South Africa, Pretoria, South Africa

E-mail: muteza@unisa.ac.za

Ashley Teedzwi Mutezo: ORCID: 000-0002-3002-0040

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Correspondence concerning this article should be addressed to

Luke Charles Chikosi, Department of Finance, Risk Management and Banking, College of Economic Management Sciences (CEMS) University of South Africa, Pretoria, South Africa

E-mail: chikosiluke@gmail.com

literature in this field of study. The third section describes the methods used to investigate the key drivers of EWRM implementation. The fourth section discusses the findings from quantitative analysis. The final portion presents the study's conclusion.

Review of Literature

Theoretical Framework

The Agency Theory: For this study, agency theory serves as the foundation of a theoretical framework. According to the agency theory, organisational silos (corporate functions) aim to maximise earnings through specialisation (Maxmudova, 2020). Usually, silos are run by managers motivated by incentives, resulting in suboptimal risk management practices through either over-management and/or under-management of certain risk categories (González et al., 2020a). Consequently, this creates the agency problem of corporate risk management.

However, the board of directors (BoD) is perceived to be risk-neutral and represents the shareholders' interests. As such, BoD pursues the maximisation of long-term firm value (Dionne, 2019; González et al., 2020a). In this regard, the BoD understands the agency's problem of risk management and is empowered to mobilise firm resources. On the same note, the BoD experiences "the information asymmetry problem of corporate risk management" (Klučka & Grünbichler, 2020). This problem is caused by the board's lack of access to information related to risks faced by the silos and their risk mitigation approaches. Consequently, the failure of the BoD to assess the firm's overall risk profile. To circumvent the shortfalls of silo-based risk management, the BoD takes measures to aggregate information about net risk exposures centrally in the firm (Jankensgård, 2019b; Klučka & Grünbichler, 2020). In this regard, the BoD adopts monitoring mechanisms and incentive systems to overcome the agency problems of corporate risk management.

Furthermore, to perform risk governance and risk aggregation, the BoD invests in novel risk management capabilities in the organisation. The extent of resource investment in groundbreaking risk management capabilities is proportional to the perceived costs related to agency and information problems of risk management (Jankensgård, 2019b). The theory of risk management resonates with the notion that EWRM is grounded on the need to improve capital efficiency, improve shareholder earnings, and reduce expected costs of external capital and regulatory compliance.

Critical Success Factors Theory: Critical success theory, as proposed by Rockart (1979) emphasises the need for a board of directors to concentrate on the activities that have a significant effect on the firm's ability to attain its objectives. Rockart (1979) defines critical factors as activity functions that the board of directors must continuously and diligently assess. Each area's present performance should be measured regularly.

The existing literature asserts that essential success criteria for mining corporations implementing EWRM include, but are not limited to, cross-functional teams, regulatory compliance, digitalisation, globalisation, corporate governance, and organisational risk management culture. These success factors are crucial to the embracing of the integrated management of risks instead of the "silo" risk management approach in the mining firms. Importantly, the board of directors need to acknowledge these factors as key drivers to EWRM.

Method

Participants

This study is a cross-sectional study based on drivers for EWRM data in the South African mining sector for the year ended 31 March 2024. The population of the study included Sixty-seven mining firms affiliated with the Mineral Council of South Africa (MCSA) as of 31 March 2024. Data were collected from risk management practitioners using a five-point Likert scale questionnaire. The risk practitioners who were requested to complete the questionnaire were the risk manager, the finance manager, the portfolio manager, the operations manager, and the internal auditor.

Measures

Description of Variables: The independent and dependent variables for this study are the drivers of Enterprise-Wide Risk Management (EWRM) and the implementation of EWRM, respectively. The drivers of Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) encompass the factors that influence and shape an organisation's risk management strategy (Muslih, 2019). These drivers can be either internal or external and are vital in how a company identifies, assesses, and mitigates potential risks in the pursuit of its objectives. An extensive literature review identified 34 drivers for EWRM for this study. Implementation of EWRM in the South African mining industry, in this study, is measured on a five-point Likert scale based on the risk practitioners' ratings. The risk practitioners were requested to rate the impact of each EWRM driver on the extent of EWRM implementation.

Measurement Instruments: A purposive sampling technique was employed to gather quantitative primary data from risk practitioners within the South African mining sector using a questionnaire survey designed on a five-point Likert scale. The scale ranged from 1 to 5, where 1 represented "very insignificant," 2 indicated "insignificant," 3 was "neutral," 4 signified "significant," and 5 denoted "very significant."

Sample Adequacy: Sphericity and measure of sample adequacy were performed using Bartlett's test and KaiserMayerOlkin (KMO), respectively. The KMO was confirmed to be 0.628, indicating that each construct had been projected equally by other constructs, devoid of error. The general KMO value is more than the acceptable value of 0.5 as per Kaiser's (1974) recommendations. Kaiser (1974) states that the least KMO value is 0.5, and the values between 0.5 and 0.6 are mediocre, whilst values of 0.7, 0.8, and 0.9 are considered good, very good, and excellent, respectively. Bartlett's test of sphericity value was 5801.469 and significant at $p=0.000$, which was below 0.05, which was significant at a 99% confidence level. This shows that the correlations among variables in the data were not singular or an identity correlation matrix (Razali, Wahid, Adnan, & Hilmi, 2024). These outcome points indicated that the correlations were solid enough for carrying out a factor analysis on the items. Table 1 presents KMO and Bartlett's test results.

Table 1

KMO and Bartlett's Test Results

Kaiser-Mayer-Olkin measure of sample adequacy		.628
Bartlett's test for sphericity	Approximate Chi-Square	5801.469
	df	1770
	Sig	.000

Note. Source: Author compilation

Reliability and Validity: Cronbach's alpha was utilized to assess the reliability of the study, which was determined to be satisfactory, as the values exceeded 0.6. Specifically, the Cronbach's coefficient values for the drivers of EWRM and the implementation of EWRM were 0.690 and 0.729, respectively, as presented in Table 2. These Cronbach's alpha values were employed to ensure content validity, and any necessary adjustments were made before distributing the questionnaire to participants.

Table 2

Cronbach's Alpha

Construct	Cronbach's Alpha Value
Drivers for EWRM	0.690
EWRM implementation	0.729

Note. Source: Author's compilation

Procedure

The questionnaire was created based on drivers for the EWRM literature review. The questionnaire was pre-tested by distributing it to fifteen (15) risk practitioners from mining companies to revise it in line with the feedback from risk management practitioners. The questionnaire was distributed electronically to 335 risk practitioners from MCSA-member mining firms, including internal auditors, finance managers, portfolio managers, risk managers, and operations managers.

The drivers for EWRM, as well as the elements of EWRM implementation, were extracted from the literature study and converted into questionnaire items. Each mining firm was requested to complete five questionnaires, and 46 mining companies submitted a total of 136 completed questionnaires. The response rate was 41%, which was slightly higher than the norm of 30-40% for online or e-mail questionnaire surveys (Nayak & Narayan, 2019).

Data Analysis

Presentation and analysis of the research findings on the influence of drivers for EWRM practices in the mining sector of South Africa are presented using measures of central tendency and dispersion, and inferential statistics.

Measures of Central Tendency and Dispersion

The demographic features of the participants that were analysed using descriptive statistics include age, education, operation, and designation.

Firstly, the demographic features of the participants were analysed using measures of central tendency. The distribution of age groups of risk practitioners ranged from below 30 years to 59 years. The age groups of participants were ranked in terms of percentages: 40-49 years (49.3%), 30-39 (38.2%), 50-59 (9.6%), and below 30 years (2.9%). The results confirmed that the majority of risk practitioners fall in the 40-49 years age group, with 49.3%. The standard deviation (8.14) was found to be less than the mean age (40.76 years), confirming low variability within the dataset. Thus,

data is normally distributed without extreme values.

The second demographic strand was the post level in the firm. Risk management positions identified in mining firms are risk manager, finance manager, portfolio manager, operations manager, and internal auditor. Risk managers constituted the highest percentage of participants (39.7%), followed by finance managers (25.7%), operation managers (11.80%), internal auditors (21.3%), and portfolio managers (1.5%). On average, risk practitioners hold the position of finance manager with a mean value of 24.93. The standard deviation (14.51) was found to be less than the mean (24.93), suggesting low variability among risk management positions' data in the South African mining sector.

The third demographic strand was the participants' level of education, classified into matric, certificate or diploma, professional-accredited, undergraduate, postgraduate diploma, or doctoral qualification. The results confirmed that the majority of risk practitioners in the mining sector (51.5%) have postgraduate qualifications, followed by professional accreditations (35.3%), certificates or diplomas (8.8%), undergraduate degrees (3.7%), and no matriculation (0.7%). The mean value of 16.3 in the age group strand suggests that, on average, risk management practitioners in the mining sector hold at least a National Senior Certificate. The standard deviation (14.53) is less than the mean value of 24.93, indicating low variability within risk management positions.

Finally, the mining company's operational period was examined. It was discovered that 81.6 percent of MCSA mining firms have been in operation for more than 20 years. On average, South African mining firms have been in operation for 22.6 years, suggesting resilience supported by sound enterprise-wide risk management practices. The standard deviation of 3.13, which is far less than the mean value of 22.6, confirms low variability among the dataset.

The analysis of age, level of education, and managerial position of research participants details the extent of diversity within the risk management fraternity (Bhat et al., 2020; Sarhan et al., 2019). Diversity in the workplace is thought to provide benefits such as increased productivity, improved skill diversity, mentorship opportunities, and increased employee retention (Sarhan et al., 2019). Furthermore, age diversity among risk practitioners is critical because different age groups perceive risks differently (Sarhan et al., 2019). Young risk practitioners, for example, are dynamic, innovative, and risk takers, whereas risk practitioners over the age of 40 are thought to be risk averse. The number of years a company has been in business is also important in confirming the resilience of its internal risk management processes (Bag et al., 2022; Lund et al., 2020). The age diversity among risk practitioners is critical because it allows for mentorship relationships between older serving employees and younger employees, fostering effective EWRM (Gomez & Bernet, 2019).

The demographic features of the participants are summarised in Table 3.

Table 3: Demographic Characteristics

Variable	Observations	Modal class	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max	Range
Age	136	5	40.76	8.14	0	59	59
Position	136	5	24.93	14.51	2	35	33
Education level	136	5	16.3	2.51	11	18	7
Years in operation	136	5	22.6	3.13	0	20	20

Note. Source: Author compilation

Inferential Statistical Analysis

To determine the effect of drivers for EWRM on EWRM implementation, inferential statistical analysis: confirmatory analysis, correlation analysis, and analysis of variance (ANOVA) were employed. Correlation matrix and ANOVA were used to establish the relationship between the predictor (drivers for EWRM) and the response variables (ERWM implementation).

Confirmatory Factor Analysis: Using variance analysis, 72.823% cumulative variance was attributed to 15 factors, namely legal and

regulatory compliance requirements, globalisation, credit rating agency requirements, better risk reporting, a broader scope of risks, competitive advantage, improved resource distribution, enhanced client satisfaction, better control over enterprise projects, advances in technology, greater management consensus, increased management accountability, appeal and reinforcement from top management, better decision-making, and improved risk recording and communication. Table 4 presents the cumulative variance explained for the factors.

Table 4
Cumulative Variance Explained for the Factors

Component	Initial eigenvalues			Extraction sum of squared loadings		
	Total	% of variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of variance	Cumulative %
1	9.383	15.639	15.639	9.383	15.639	15.639
2	6.174	10.290	25.929	6.174	10.290	25.929
3	4.741	7.902	33.831	4.741	7.902	33.831
4	3.725	6.208	40.038	3.725	6.208	40.038
5	2.899	4.832	44.870	2.899	4.832	44.870
6	2.778	4.630	49,500	2.778	4.630	49,500
7	2.266	3.777	53.277	2.266	3.777	53.277
8	1.905	3.175	56.452	1.905	3.175	56.452
9	1.887	3.146	59.598	1.887	3.146	59.598
10	1,700	2.833	62.431	1,700	2.833	62.431
11	1.589	2.649	65.080	1.589	2.649	65.080
12	1.368	2.280	67.359	1.368	2.280	67.359
13	1.146	1.911	69.270	1.146	1.911	69.270
14	1.089	1.815	71.085	1.089	1.815	71.085
15	1.043	1.738	72.823	1.043	1.738	72.823

Note. Source: Author compilation

Correlation Analysis: A scatterplot was used to determine the correlation between dependent and independent variables. The correlation coefficient between EWRM drivers and EWRM implementation in South Africa's mining sector was 0.266, which was statistically significant at $p=0.000$. A negative correlation between

EWRM drivers and EWRM implementation means that as one variable rises, the other falls (Anselin, 2019). A scatterplot also shows the strength and direction of the relationship between the predictor and response variables (Lee, 2020; Watanabe & Mizukami, 2019). The study discovered a positive relationship between EWRM drivers and EWRM implementation. The proximity of dots on the scatterplot, as shown in Figure 1, explains the relationship.

Figure 1
Scatterplot

Note. Source: Author compilation

Analysis of Variance: ANOVA was used to determine the extent to which the drivers for EWRM influence EWRM implementation. As shown in Table 5, the drivers for EWRM are statistically insignificant to EWRM implementation in South Africa's mining sector. The p-values of EWRM drivers were greater than 0.05. This means that drivers for EWRM were only responsible for 16.6 per cent of EWRM implementation.

Table 5
ANOVA Coefficients

Model		Unstandardised coefficients		Standardised	t	Sig.
		B	Std error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	0.772***	0.759		1.018	0.000
	B	0.166**	-0.040	-0.040	-0.664	.508

Note. t statistics in parentheses *** $p < 0.001$, * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, Source: Author compilation

Results and Discussion

Participants were requested to complete the questionnaire on the influence of drivers on EWRM-on-EWRM implementation. Critical

drivers for EWRM management were determined using the normalised mean values. Overall mean scores of 34 drivers for EWRM ranged from 3.000 to 4.860. The top ten EWRM drivers were ranked based on the inclusive average scores as shown in Table 6.

Table 6
Drivers for EWRM Rankings

Rank	Code	Driver	Overall mean	Normalised values
1	B25	Health, safety, and environment	4.8750	0.9375
2	B1	Legal and regulatory compliance requirements	4.8603	0.9301
3	B27	Catastrophic events	4.8529	0.9265
4	B5	A broader scope of risks	4.7721	0.8861
5	B29	Unanticipated losses	4.6985	0.8493
6	B33	Corporate governance	4.5147	0.7574
7	B15	Better risk reporting and communication	4.4779	0.7390
8	B16	Competitive advantage	4.4559	0.7280
9	B2	Globalisation	4.4265	0.7135
10	B28	Risk management standards	4.3897	0.6949

Note. Source: Author

Drivers with normalised values equivalent to 0.5000 or above were considered critical. In this study, two out of 34 drivers for EWRM were found not to be critical. Based on the study, the top ten drivers for EWRM implementation in the South African mining sector are discussed as follows:

Overall, health, safety, and the environment (B25) were recognised as the most powerful driving forces for EWRM implementation in the mining sector of South Africa. However, the study by Zhao et al. (2015) in the construction industry of Singapore found regulatory compliance as the major driver for EWRM implementation. The mining companies in South Africa adopted a 'zero harm' principle to eliminate accidents in mines (Koh, 2020). The 'zero harm' principle is also supported by the Mine Health and Safety Act of 1996 (Act 29 of 1996) (Stewart et al., 2020). The Mine Health and Safety Act (29 of 1996) makes provision that mining firms should supply sufficient health and safety gear as well as training and development and should respond to any form of risk or hazard to which workers might be exposed (Nalule, 2019). This implies that health, safety, and the environment are not just a matter of policy but also a regulatory requirement that drives the implementation of EWRM in South African mines (González et al., 2020b). Mineworkers are exposed to risks such as gas explosions, shaft collapse, and occupational diseases such as tuberculosis, silicosis, and noise-induced hearing loss. The South African mining sector suffered 73 fatalities in 2016 compared to 77 in 2015, thus a decrease of 5% (Stewart et al., 2020).

Legal and regulatory compliance requirements (B1) were recognised as the second most powerful driving force behind EWRM implementation in the South African mining sector. South African mining law is regulated by the Mineral and Petroleum Resources Development Act, 28 of 2002 (MPRDA), which is a principal piece of legislation dealing with acquirements or rights to perform reconnaissance, prospecting, mining, and closure of mines (Bowman, 2019). According to Nalule (2019), other pieces of legislation regulate the operation of mining companies in South Africa, such as

- the Mineral and Petroleum Resources Development Act of 2002 [MPRDA] (28 of 2002).
- the Mining Titles Registration Act of 1967 [MTRA] (16 of 1967).
- the Mine Health and Safety Act of 1996 [MHSA] (29 of 1996); and
- the Minerals Act of 1991 [MA] (50 of 1991).

The mining industry in South Africa operates in a dynamic and complex regulatory and legislative environment. Regular changes in government legislation and regulation increase uncertainty, raise costs, and jeopardise investor returns, while increasing reliance on healthy stakeholder relationships (Fernandez, 2019; Stuermer, 2018). The introduction of the Mining Charter (Nalule, 2019) by the DMR, for example, is viewed as a threat to the smooth operation of the South African mining sector by MCSA. Furthermore, failure to comply with any MPRDA provision by a mining company in South Africa results in severe penalties such as fines, cancellation of an operating license, and imprisonment of directors (Bowman, 2019). As a result, effective EWRM implementation improves regulatory compliance in the mining industry. Furthermore, rising international and domestic regulatory pressure, the likelihood of financial distress, overheads, poor earnings performance, and the availability of growth opportunities all play important roles in encouraging EWRM (Anton & Nucu, 2020).

Catastrophic events (B27), such as mine flooding and sinkholes, as well as events such as the Marikana massacre in 2012, are regarded as the third most influential driver of EWRM in the South African mining sector. The sinkhole collapse at Lily Mine in Mpumalanga in August 2016 (Economy, 2021a) which killed three miners, is one of the catastrophic events in South Africa's mining sector that demonstrates why mining companies must implement EWRM. The magnitude of the threat posed by catastrophic events in the South African mining sector suggests that EWRM implementation can be used as a strategy to mitigate or reduce losses caused by catastrophic events.

A broader scope of risks (B5) ranked fourth in the drivers

for EWRM rankings, implying that mining companies in South Africa implemented EWRM to address new risks that emerged in the business environment. (Bohnert et al., 2019) support the findings by stating that for EWRM to be useful to an organisation, it must address risks such as compliance risk, credit risk, cyber information security risk, financial risk, legal risk, operational risk, reputational risk, and strategic risk. (Hillson, 2023) agrees that EWRM manages all forms of risk.

The fifth on the EWRM rankings was unanticipated losses (B29), implying that mining companies in South Africa implemented EWRM to minimise the downside impact of unanticipated losses such as a sudden stoppage in production due to safety issues or labour unrest. For instance, the labour unrest that induced the tragic Marikana massacre in 2012 resulted in the Johannesburg Securities Exchange Mining Index plummeting lower than the Global Mining Index (Economy, 2021a). Also, Kumba iron ore suffered an unexpected decrease in production in August 2013 due to pit constraints and safety stoppages (Economy, 2021a). Unexpected events entailing safety stoppages and violent labour unrest may result in huge losses; hence, there is a need to implement EWRM in the mining sector of South Africa to mitigate the risk exposure thereof. An effective EWRM program would not only cut down the cost but could also make available beneficial time and resources to concentrate on individual business solutions (Muslih, 2019). Accordingly, enterprises that expect to face substantial types of risk may utilise EWRM to create a competitive advantage (Bohnert et al., 2019).

Corporate governance (B33) was ranked sixth, indicating that EWRM implementation in the South African mining sector is now considered standard practice. Corporate governance issues in the mining industry included political influence, fraud, and controversial deals, as well as mismanagement and negligence. One example of poor corporate governance in the South African mining sector is the liquidation of Aurora Empowerment Systems Mine in 2011 due to two years of unpaid wages and a lack of a risk management system (Cornelissen et al., 2019; Saenz, 2019). In addition, in March 2016, Oakby Investments, a shareholder of Shiva Uranium, cut ties with its stakeholders (FNB, ABSA, KPMG, and Sasfin) due to the political influence of the former president Jacob Zuma. In addition, Bowman (2019) points out that the stakeholders of Oakby Investments cut ties in order to protect themselves against reputational risk. The closure of Aurora Empowerment Systems' mine and the cutting of ties between Oakby Investments and its stakeholders due to poor corporate governance practices serve as motivation for mining companies to initiate and implement EWRM (Corrigan, 2019). As a result, EWRM is expected to be integrated into management's day-to-day activities in the South African mining sector. Chen et al. (2020) support this position by stating that good corporate governance and EWRM are critical to the entity's stabilisation, sustainability, and growth. Good corporate governance and EWRM are linked to help entities understand risks, meet organisational objectives, and reduce, assess, and manage risk appropriately. Furthermore, Bohnert et al. (2019) state that external variables such as corporate governance, laws, and regulatory compliances influence a concrete decision to use EWRM. Thus, the outcomes of this research are in tandem with previous studies (Zhao et al., 2015; Oliveira et al., 2019).

Better risk reporting and communication (B15) was ranked seventh on the list of drivers for EWRM rankings, implying that

mining companies in South Africa should implement EWRM to improve risk reporting and communication. Hillson (2023) asserts that effective risk reporting enables proactive risk management by allowing firms to identify and escalate concerns as they emerge or before they are recognised to take a proactive approach to risk mitigation. Still, Shatnawi and Eldaia (2020) emphasise that effective risk reporting encourages openness about exposures and encourages sustained improvement by emphasising areas of concern within an entity and focusing on how risk activities affect strategic business units and commercial risk profiles. As a result, EWRM implementation aids in improving communication and reporting on risks faced by South African mining companies. Firms should improve risk communication to capitalise on opportunities and boost confidence in risk management. Furthermore, the communication of the organisation's risk should be effective enough to guarantee that the risk appetite is built at the lower echelons of management (Bohnert et al., 2019; Fraser et al., 2021).

In the eighth position of the drivers for EWRM rankings was reduced costs and losses (B16), implying that EWRM implementation by South African mining companies assists in reducing costs and losses. Muslih (2019) points out that the value effects of risk management at the enterprise level are mostly indirect, which possibly diminishes the expenses allied with conflicts of interest amongst owners and managers. Mining projects generally involve extreme risk exposure as well as the prospect of huge losses. Challenging operational environments, such as high operating costs, mineral ore grade in the platinum sector, and deep mine shafts in the gold sector, reduce the profit margins of mining entities (Corrigan, 2019; Stuermer, 2018; Urbina & Rodríguez, 2023).

Globalisation (B2) is ranked number nine in terms of influencing the implementation of EWRM practices in the South African mining sector. This implies that global risks, such as exchange rate volatility and a drop in mineral prices on the international market, also affect South African mining companies since these companies are international players. The global financial turmoil of 2008 led to a decrease in production in the mining sector. For example, diamond production in South Africa decreased because of global economic crises and pressure on disposable earnings (Economy, 2021b). Minerals like gold and platinum have suffered a decline in prices since 2008. Gold decreased by 32%, and platinum decreased by 31% (PwC, 2020). The decrease in prices was a result of a subdued global commodities aggregate demand. Mining companies in South Africa need to implement effective EWRM measures to minimise losses due to their international exposure. Oliveira et al. (2019) state that the influences that have motivated companies to approach risk management in an integrated way are globalisation and technological advancement.

The tenth-ranked driver for EWRM implementation in the South African mining sector was risk management standards (B28), suggesting that EWRM implementation is on the rise because of numerous risk management standards that have been implemented to help companies mitigate their losses and enhance their performance. Examples of risk management frameworks, among others, include

- the Cadbury and Turnbull Report on Corporate Governance in the United Kingdom (Shah & Napier, 2017).
- the King Reports in South Africa (King, 2020).
- COSO's EWRM integrated framework in the United States (Yuan, 2022).

- the Australian/New Zealand Risk Management Standard (Perera, 2019).

The research revealed that mining companies in South Africa are facing a wide array of risks that affect their daily operations and long-term existence; hence, the need to implement EWRM. The extent of EWRM implementation in the South African mining sector was found to be strongly linked to its drivers. Through an extensive literature review, 34 drivers for EWRM in the South African mining sector were identified.

The primary objective of the study was to investigate the critical drivers for EWRM influencing EWRM implementation in the South African mining sector. The findings showed that there were 34 drivers for EWRM implementation. Furthermore, drivers for EWRM were determined by calculating normalised values, and drivers with normalised values above 0.500 were considered critical. The research concluded that there were 32 critical drivers for EWRM in the mining sector of South Africa. Also, average mean scores ranging from 3.000 to 4.8603 were used to rank drivers for EWRM implementation.

The secondary objective of the study was to determine the influence of drivers for EWRM on EWRM implementation in the South African mining sector. This objective was achieved through analysis of variance (ANOVA). Drivers for EWRM were found to be insignificant to the implementation of EWRM in the mining sector. The p-value of drivers for EWRM was above 0.05, indicating that it was statistically insignificant. Drivers for EWRM were only responsible for 16.6% of EWRM implementation in the mining sector. Moreover, through correlation analysis, it was concluded that there was a negative relationship between drivers for EWRM and EWRM implementation in the mining sector ($r=-0.309$).

Conclusion

The study investigated critical drivers for EWRM implementation in the South African mining companies that are MCSA members. Through an extensive literature review, 34 drivers for EWRM were identified. The data relating to drivers for EWRM in South African mining companies were gathered by means of a questionnaire and analysed using ANOVA and correlation techniques. Drivers for EWRM implementation in South Africa were ranked using the overall mean scores. Thirty-two (32) drivers for EWRM were considered critical because their normalised values were above 0.5000. Conversely, two drivers were considered not critical because their normalised values were below 0.5000.

Health and safety issues are considered one of the critical drivers for EWRM in the South African mining sector, according to this study. Moreover, the study recommends that mining companies should implement EWRM to promote the health and safety of their employees. Future studies could investigate the influence of the drivers for EWRM on the elements of the EWRM framework in non-extractive industries. Such studies may enhance the implementation of EWRM in all sectors, thereby increasing the effectiveness of risk mitigation strategies across the key economic sectors. Moreover, research on drivers for EWRM could be done using interviews so that the real voices and opinions of participants would be understood. In the future, researchers may also employ structural equation modelling to establish the relationship between drivers for EWRM and elements of EWRM in the mining sector of South Africa.

Furthermore, the findings of the study contribute to the existing body of knowledge, policy formulation, and risk management performance. Firstly, the study contributes to the body of knowledge by concentrating on the factors driving EWRM implementation in mining companies that are members of MCSA. The findings of this study may be used as a basis for research on drivers for EWRM in other economic sectors in South Africa and beyond. The findings of the study also add value to an understanding of drivers for EWRM in business entities. Secondly, the study findings may assist regulators and government agencies to formulate and implement EWRM policies, guidelines, and frameworks that would enhance the implementation of EWRM. The government could enact regulations that would minimise the impact and frequency of critical risks in the mining sector.

The mining companies in South Africa, both MCSA members and non-members, could use the research findings to identify critical drivers for EWRM to improve firm-wide risk management performance. Risk managers will be able to establish risk management policies tailored to their organisations after identifying and ranking a comprehensive updated list of EWRM drivers. Furthermore, the study's findings may encourage mining companies' top management to take the lead in embracing EWRM implementation and its perceived benefits. Furthermore, the findings of this study substantiate the importance of EWRM in the survival of mining companies in South Africa's dynamic business environment. Consequently, the findings could provide insight into drivers for EWRM implementation for risk practitioners in the mining sector. Mining companies could use drivers for EWRM identified as critical factors to bolster their risk management policies and techniques.

As a result, mining companies are recommended to develop risk management strategies to strengthen EWRM implementation. Additionally, senior management should take the lead in implementing EWRM in the mining sector to promote and consolidate a holistic risk management culture and reap the ostensible benefits of EWRM. The board's support and commitment should be visible and ongoing, demonstrating to employees the importance of implementing EWRM. Furthermore, top management needs to explicitly establish the enterprise's risk policies and procedures in the form of a risk policy document, and the board must then ensure that the risk policies are enforced at all levels of the firm.

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